

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

An HM-Net Preprocessing Framework for Gastrointestinal Cancer Endoscopy Image Enhancement

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Abstract

Objectives: GI endoscopy images frequently suffers from illumination artifacts, specular reflection, low contrast and texture inconsistencies, to address pre-processing challenges the proposed HM-Net framework integrates HSV colour space transformation with morphological operations for effective enhancement of endoscopic images prior to classification. **Method:** The proposed HM-Net framework initially applies image resizing, Gaussian filtering, intensity normalization to standardize the endoscopy images. Subsequently, RGB images are transformed into the HSV color space to independently manipulate brightness and chromatic information. Illuminations are suppressed by saturation values (S) followed by CLAHE guided enhancement on V channel are applied. Furthermore, by applying adaptive thresholding a binary lesion mask is generated and morphological opening and closing operations are employed to refine lesion boundaries. The proposed framework uses the generated binary masks as a lesion guided preprocessing inputs for CNN based classification. The enhanced images are subsequently classified using EfficientNet-B0 into three clinically regrouped categories such as Normal, inflammation and Cancer. **Findings:** The performance of the proposed HM-Net framework is evaluated using objective image quality measures, such as peak-signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and structural similarity index measure (SSIM), on the publicly available Kvasir-v2 dataset. The HM-Net algorithm achieves a higher PSNR and SSIM values of 39.2 dB and 0.994, respectively. **Novelty:** HM-Net novel framework achieves significant enhancement of higher PSNR and SSIM over baselines and substantially reduces the false positive rates. It significantly outperforms compare to generic methods and matches recent tailored algorithms on standard benchmarks. This hybrid approach is novel in gastrointestinal imaging and yields clear lesion contrast.

Keywords: Gastrointestinal Cancer; Endoscopic Images; Image Enhancement; HSV Transformation; Morphological Filtering; Image Processing

1 Introduction

Recent GI endoscopy imaging techniques use contrast enhancement and filtering methods to improve lesion visibility. However, many such methods amplify noise in low light regions; color space methods highlight lesions but often neglect fine details. To address these gaps HM-Net has been proposed. HM-Net is a hybrid HSV morphology framework that enhances lesion contrast while suppressing noise.

Recent developments in GI endoscopy image analysis has demonstrated the effectiveness of hybrid enhancement and segmentation framework for improving lesion visibility and diagnosis reliability. Several deep leaning based medical image segmentation approaches have focused on spatial information and boundary information in complex medical images. Ramesh et al⁽¹⁾, proposed a hybrid Kolmogorov Arnold network for medical image segmentation framework to enhance contextual feature representation based on the nonlinear adaptive representation. Although the model demonstrate improved segmentation performance whereas its computational complexity limits its applicability in lightweight preprocessing.

Masked supervised semantic segmentation approach has demonstrated improved feature consistency by utilizing partially labelled supervision and contextual masking strategies. These methods helps to reduce annotation dependency and improve segmentation accuracy but requires computational resources and pixel level annotations⁽²⁾. Furthermore, spatial context aware medical segmentation framework has emphasized the integration of local texture information and global contextual features for lesion delineation while these methods achieves strong segmentation performance whereas, these methods often depends on large annotated datasets and complex architecture which can limit their applicability in real time GI preprocessing system⁽³⁾.

In contrast to existing convolutional segmentation oriented methods, the proposed HM-Net framework focuses on lightweight lesion focused preprocessing using HSV based enhancement and morphological refinement prior to classification. Rather than performing full semantic segmentation the proposed framework generates intermediate lesion guided binary mask that enhance classification oriented feature extraction while maintaining lower computationl complexity..

Normally, images are enhanced by applying the contrast enhancement and illumination and low light enhancement techniques. The contrast enhancement techniques like histogram equalization redistribute pixel intensity across dynamic range for improving the contrast of the image by Bhrdwajeta et al⁽⁴⁾. CLAHE is an advanced image enhancement techniques used for image preprocessing that locally applies histogram equalization within small regions for avoiding over enhancement and excessive noise. CLAHE is an effective method for endoscopic images when variation of lighting condition by Moghtaderi et al⁽⁵⁾.

According to Natalia obukhova et al⁽⁶⁾ Adaptive Median filtering and non-local mean filtering is type of noise reduction and filtering technique which is applied for reducing high density noise and impulse whereas median filter preserves edge details and boundaries whereas NLM finds the similarity between image patches for achieving effective denoising. Bilateral filter is one of the noises reducing technique which reduces the noise without blurring detailed anatomical boundaries by Shiva moghtaderi et al⁽⁵⁾ and Wenyaoxia et al⁽⁷⁾.

Color space transformation techniques such as converting RGB to HSV/HSI color space allows separate manipulation of color brightness and information by Priya Bhrdwajeta et al⁽⁴⁾ and Shiva moghtaderi et al⁽⁵⁾. Adaptive thresholding and contour analysis is a type of morphological filtering which identifies region whereas contour analysis extracts boundary information and morphological processing such as dilation, erosion, opening and closing refine these boundaries⁽⁴⁾. Generally, encoder and decoder architecture is used to localize region of interest (ROI) for reducing the computational burden⁽⁸⁾. Furthermore existing methodologies are discussed in Table 1.

1.1 Overview of Computational Methods

Artificial intelligence enables machine and system to perform tasks typically requires human intelligence. Machine learning and deep learning are the subset of AI. Machine learning and deep learning models are acts as an intelligent filter in the stage of preprocessing for cleaning or removing noise, enhancing the image quality and structuring the image to detect cancer more accurately in GI endoscopy images⁽⁹⁾,⁽¹⁰⁾ machine learning and deep learning based preprocessing needed for endoscopy images to address the challenges like noise, blur and uneven illumination⁽⁹⁾,⁽¹¹⁾ CNN (Convolutional Neural network) is a deep learning architecture mainly designed for processing grid data like images convolutional neural network preserves spatial structure of data and making them highly effective for image classification, object detection and medical imaging. Architecture of CNN is shown in Figure 1. Generally CNN consists of four layers to make a final decision. Input layer takes a raw input image like 28*28 grayscale or 224*224 RGB represented as a 2D or 3D matrix of pixel value. To differentiate benign and malignant lesions in cancer CNN based systems are widely applied in medical diagnosis⁽¹²⁾.

Second layer of CNN architecture consists of convolutional layer that applies filters to the input image to extract local features like edge, color, patterns and textures. Next layer of CNN are pooling layer which reduces the spatial dimensions of feature maps.

Fig 1. CNN Architecture Diagram

Last layer of CNN model are fully connected layer also called as dense layer which flattened the output into a vector and produce the final classification or regression output.

The proposed HM-Net framework is designed for preprocessing and lesion enhancement strategy. HSV transformation and morphological operations as mentioned in **Algorithm 1** are deterministic image enhancement procedures used to enhance lesion visibility prior to the CNN based classification. These process donot contain trainable parameters. After preprocessing stage, the enhanced images are feeded as a input to the EfficientNetB0 classifier for disease classification. Here, CNN training stage and preprocessing stage are processed independently. In the proposed framework preprocessing improves the image quality and lesion localization whereas, CNN performs supervised disease classification.

To overcome these drawbacks of preprocessing, HM-Net is proposed with the combination of HSV color space and morphological operation with the help of these processes accurate cancer part is predicted from GI endoscopic images.

Challenges of Existing Methods:

- In the existing literature, endoscopic image often suffers from non-uniform illumination due to the confined internal environment.
- Presence of specular reflection caused by moist tissue surface and created bright spots.
- High intra-class variability affects the best feature extraction.
- Dataset contains uneven distribution across classes, which affects preprocessing.
- Color distortion plays a vital role in identifying GI abnormalities.
- Inaccurate lesion boundary detection due to blur edges and fails to preserve fine structural details.

The main contribution of proposed HM-Net framework is as follows:

- A novel HM-Net framework improvise the feature learning to extract best features for detecting the cancer accurately.
- A hybrid model of HSV color space with morphological operation solves the challenges like illumination, noise and artifacts present in the endoscopy images.
- A proposed HM-Net framework improves the lesion boundary representation and noise suppression.
- HM-Net framework enhances the classification performance of GI cancer detection by extracting the better features from the preprocessing model.

The proposed research is divided into three sections: Section 2 presents the Methodology of proposed HM-Net algorithm; Section 3 discusses experimental results and their comparisons; Section 4 derives the conclusions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Proposed Methodology

The experimental analysis is carried out using Kvasir-v2 publically available dataset of 8000 images. These images are resized to 224×224 and converted to HSV color space then; apply disk-shaped morphological opening and closing (radius 3-7px) to

Table 1. Literature Review of Exiting Methodologies

Ref-er-ence	Methods used	Description
(13)	This study uses Adaptive brightness equalization algorithm	This algorithm significantly improves local dark areas, texture details, and elimination of specular reflections for enhanced image quality
(14)	This study utilizes Guided filter method	This method is used to filter and smooth the low light images capture by WCE (Wireless Capsule Endoscopy)
(15)	This paper focuses on weighting and threshold based approach	This methodology is designed to enhance the image quality for maintaining the essential details
(16)	This study uses digital filters like average, median, Gaussian, and savitzky golay.	This paper evaluates and discusses several digital filters for enhancing the image quality and improves deep learning model detection for IBD polyp
(17)	This study utilizes image decomposition algorithm and weighted guided filter based on canny operator.	The methods like image decomposition separates detail and base layers followed by weighted guided filter to enhance contrast of the image and preserve vascular details in gastrointestinal endoscopy images
(18)	This study focuses on methods like LHCM (logarithm based histogram correction method) and unsharp masking in wavelet domain.	The method like LHCM is introduced to improve the contrast when avoiding artifacts and unsharp masking is applied for further detail enhancement
(19)	This study emphasises multi-step preprocessing approach like hybrid bilateral-gaussian filtering, Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE), and unsharp masking.	The methods like hybrid bilateral-gaussian filtering are used to reduce noise in images. CLAHE is applied for contrast enhancement and unsharp masking is applied for edge enhancement
(20)	This study utilizes adaptive histogram equalization (AHE).	The preprocessing methods like AHE are used to enhance the image quality and that improves the contrast and visibility of the image
(21)	This study focuses on weighted guided filtering algorithm and unsharp mask algorithm.	This paper combines weighted guided filtering algorithm and unsharp mask algorithm for enhancing vessel details and contours in the image
(22)	The study of this paper converts RGB to lab color mode.	This paper converts RGB image into lab color mode for extracting texture feature for neural network training and improve the quality of the image
(23)	This study focuses on the adaptive fraction gamma transformation and unsharp masking filter methods.	These preprocessing methodologies are focuses on improving brightness, contrast, and preserving color information
(24)	This study uses a preprocessing method such as CycleGAN (Generative Adversarial Network)	This technique applied to enhance the low quality image and aid polyp detection by improving the visual clarity

the saturation and value channels followed by contrast enhancement on V channel. Python 3.9 are used for implementing the proposed methodology. Here, a random hyper parameter such as $Cliplimit=2.5$, $tileGridSize = (8, 8)$ is used with the best practice to cover more configurations efficiently. The HM-Net framework generates enhanced lesion images that serve as input for Efficient-B0 classifier. Furthermore, the CNN model was employed for disease classification and the network was trained using categorical cross entropy loss with the adam optimizer trained up to 15 epochs with early stopping validation to avoid overfitting. The best model was selected based on validation accuracy rather than PSNR/SSIM. But, as of now PSNR/SSIM are selected for evaluating the preprocessing framework prior to classification since, PSNR/SSIM were independently used to measure the quality of the preprocessing framework by comparing enhanced images with their corresponding images.

2.2 Preprocessing of GI Endoscopy image in HM-Net

Gastrointestinal endoscopy images often suffers from strong reflections and poor lighting conditions also color variations caused by bleeding, mucus or inflammation. The causes of these factors reduce the visual distinction between abnormal and normal mucosal region. The preprocessing stage became unstable because illumination changes directly affect pixel values when images

are processed in the RGB color space. The proposed methodology such as HM-Net algorithm is introduced to address these challenges. The architecture diagram for HM-Net is shown in Figure 2.

Algorithm 1. HM-Net algorithm for preprocessing endoscopy images
Input: RGB raw endoscopy images
Output: Cleaned and enhanced endoscopy images

1. Read the input image ($I_{RGB}(x,y)$)
2. Resize the image into a fixed size 224×224
3. Scale pixel range value to $[0,1]$
4. Enhance color in HSV color space ($I_{HSV}(x,y)$)
5. Normalize with mean/std
6. Convert image to grayscale
7. Create threshold for binary mask
8. Apply morphological operation ($A \circ B$) & ($A \bullet B$)
9. Display the enhanced image (I_{out})

Fig 2. The workflow of proposed preprocessing Architecture of HM-Net

2.3 Color Space Transformation

The proposed HM-Net algorithm takes the raw GI endoscopic image (RGB) and that is converted to HSV color space transformation to enhance color separation for better feature extraction. From this transformation hue and saturation captures characteristics of tissue color when abnormal gastrointestinal region is compared to healthy mucosa then abnormal region

presents distinct color patterns and higher saturation levels after conversion of RGB to HSV then binary mask is generated by applying threshold value on hue and saturation. This step isolates regions that exhibit color characteristics associated with abnormal tissue while suppressing background areas and specular highlights.

Normally, HSV separates the color information from brightness which is most suitable for image processing, feature extraction and segmentation for medical imaging. In HSV color transformation H (Hue) represents the type of color, S (Saturation) represents the purity of the color and V (Value) represents the brightness of the color. This type of color transformation allows more robust processing for finding lesion areas in endoscopic images even when illumination condition varies.

Let the input image is indicated in **Equation (1)**.

$$I_{RGB}(x,y) = (R_{(x,y)}, G_{(x,y)}, B_{(x,y)}) \tag{1}$$

Where, $R_{(x,y)}, G_{(x,y)}, B_{(x,y)}$ represents red intensity, green intensity, and blue intensity respectively. The Value (V) is computed based on the maximum intensity of the RGB values like $V = \text{Max}(R, G, B)$. Similarly, the Saturation (S) is computed based on the minimum intensity of the RGB Values like $S = \text{Min}(R, G, B)$ the S is calculated and indicated in **Equation (2)**.

$$S = \begin{cases} 0, & V = 0 \\ \frac{V - s}{V}, & V \neq 0 \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Finally, Hue (H) is calculated and shown in **Equation (3)**. It ensures numerical stability during the color space transformation.

$$H = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } Max = Min \\ 60^\circ \times \frac{G - B}{Max - Min}, & \text{if } Max = R \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Then the threshold is applied to detect the abnormal or lesion region are indicated in **Equation (4)**.

$$Mask(x,y) = \begin{cases} 1, & V(x,y) > T_v \text{ and } S(x,y) > T_x \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

Whereas, T represents the threshold value and Mask(x,y) represents the binary image. The outcome of preprocessing stage highlights the most relevant information and reduces the irrelevant Information.

2.4 Morphological Operation

The binary mask may contain small gaps, isolated pixels or discontinuities along lesion boundaries. To address these challenges morphological operations are performed to refine the mask. Erosion, dilation, opening and closing are the four types of morphological operations are present from this erosion and openings are used to remove small noisy region whereas dilation and closing restores lesion continuity and fill internal gaps. A morphological operation helps to clean up the mask and make lesion boundaries smoother and connects to broken parts of the regions. The proposed work performs opening and closing operations to clean up the mask. The opening and closing operations are computed and shown in **Equation (5) and (6)**.

$$A \circ B = (A \ominus B) \oplus B \tag{5}$$

$$A \bullet B = (A \oplus B) \ominus B \tag{6}$$

Normally, opening operation is a combination of erosion followed by dilation for removing the small noise objects, smooth boundaries and for preserving large structures similarly, closing operation is a combination of dilation followed by erosion for filling small holes of the image and connect nearby regions. Final outcome of the morphological operation is indicated in **Equation (7)**.

$$I_{out} = (A \circ B) \bullet B \tag{7}$$

HM-Net is compared to traditional preprocessing approaches, this pipeline offers several advantages. Spatial filtering techniques such as median or Gaussian filtering lead to blurred lesion boundaries and suppress fine texture patterns, which are important

for diagnosis. Contrast enhancement methods such as histogram equalization and CLAHE may increase noise and alter natural color distributions. Intensity normalization primarily addresses brightness variation but does not manipulate color cues that are essential for distinguishing abnormal tissue. Even though advanced denoising methods can preserve edges, they are computationally expensive and may remove subtle lesion details. Edge-based techniques are highly sensitive to noise and often produce fragmented boundaries.

2.5 Performance Evaluation Methods and Implementation

The outcome of the proposed HM-Net algorithm performance is calculated using the PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio) and SSIM (Structural Similarity index). PSNR usually computes the difference between the raw input image and the processed image. The result of the higher PSNR value indicates better image quality. Normally, when the PSNR value is < 20 dB then it represents the poor image quality and > 40 dB represents the high quality preprocessed image. The computation of PSNR value is shown in Equation (8) and (9).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{UV} \sum_{i=1}^U \sum_{j=1}^V [I(i, j) - K(i, j)]^2 \tag{8}$$

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{MAX^2}{MSE} \right) \tag{9}$$

Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) calculates the similarity between the two images i and j. The computation of SSIM is shown in Equation (10). The result of SSIM ranges from 0 to 1.0 where the value 0 represents the no similarity between the images and 0.9 to 1.0 represents higher similarity between two images.

$$SSIM(i, j) = \frac{(2\mu_i \mu_j + D1)(2\sigma_{ij} + D2)}{(\mu_i^2 + \mu_j^2 + D1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + D2)} \tag{10}$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Dataset and Experimental Scheme

The proposed framework uses Kvasir-v2 Dataset. It is a publically available medical endoscopic image dataset. It is particularly used for developing AI based algorithms for detection, classification of GI cancer and GI diseases. This dataset contain 8000 images with separate 8 classes (dyed lifted polyps, Dyed Resection Margins, Esophagitis, Normal Cecum, Normal Pylorus, Normal Z-Line, Polyps, Ulcerative colitis) and each class has 1000 images and each image has image size of 720*576 pixels. The sample images of 8 classes are shown in Figure 3. In the proposed work after completion of preprocessing stage and when moving toward to classification stage these 8 classes are regrouped into 3 classes as Normal category (Normal Cecum, Normal Pylorus, Normal Z-line), inflammation category (Esophagitis, Ulcerative Colitis), and Cancer (Polyp, DyedLifted Polyp, Dyed Resection Margins) for better evaluation. Training patches and specification are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Specification of training patches for the Train set, Validation set, and Test set in the dataset

Set	Train set	Validation set	Test set	Total
Normal	2100	450	450	3000
Inflammation	1400	300	300	2000
Cancer	2100	450	450	3000
Total	5600	1200	1200	8000

3.2 The Proposed Delineation Performance Metrics for the Preprocessed HM-Net Algorithm

The preprocessed endoscopic images are more processed with the proposed HM-Net algorithm for segmenting the cancer part. The training and validation outcome of the HM-Net calculated by loss and accuracy curve of preprocessed images discussed in Figure 4 (a). The outcome of the HM-Net is calculated with PSNR and SSIM performance metrics as well as analysing the

Fig 3. Sample image of Kvasir-v2 Dataset

performance metrics of HM-Net with fusion of existing algorithms like 3D Median, CLAHE, NLM, Intensity normalization, Histogram and Canny edge detection HM-Net show a best outcome with highest PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio) as 39.2 dB and SSIM (Structural Similarity Index Measure) as 0.991 are shown in Figure 4 (b) with bar chart representation.

3.3 The Proposed Performance Metrics Compared with an Existing Methodology of the GI cancer prediction Images

The performance of proposed framework is evaluated with the help of kvasir-v2 dataset. This dataset has nearly 8 classes (Dyed-lifted polyps, Dyed resection margins, Esophagitis, Normal cecum, Normal pylorus, Normal z-line, polyps, Ulcerative colitis), which are grouped into three classes for this performance evaluation as normal, inflammation, and cancer. Based on these grouping outcomes of proposed delineation of intermediate binary mask and their performance is assessed using PSNR and SSIM with the existing methodologies. The binary mask shown in Figure 5 corresponding to intermediate enhanced lesion binary mask generated in the preprocessing stage as mentioned in algorithm 1. These mask are obtained by integrating the HSV and morphological operation and are used to emphasize diagnostically relevant region prior to classification stage. and the intermediate binary mask value of the fusion methods with the 8 classes are shown in Figure 6.

Finally, the performance of HM-Net framework is compared with recent GI enhancement studies are shown in Table 3. Guo Zhang *et al*⁽²⁵⁾ applied a weighted guided filter to 200 endoscopic images (private data) this reports achieved PSNR =32.6 dB and SSIM=0.939. Rahman *et al*⁽²⁶⁾ demonstrated that EfficientNet combined with augmentation improves diagnostic accuracy but still it depends heavily on quality of preprocessing. Similarly, Abd EI- Ghany *et al*⁽²⁷⁾ achieved improved detection accuracy using deep learning based enhancement but it has higher computational complexity. When compared to these methods the proposed HM-Net provides a computational efficient preprocessing solution with maintaining high image fidelity.

HM-Net based preprocessing significantly improves lesion visibility shown in Figure 4 which produces a clear boundary of the tumor area compared to the original image also quantitatively evaluated HM-Net against baseline methods of 3D median filter, CLAHE, NLM are shown in Figure 6. HM-Net novelty lies in hybrid HSV with Morphological framework and end-to-end CNN evaluation unlike Guo Zhang *et al*⁽²⁵⁾, HM-Net jointly processes Hue/Saturation and value which leading to more vivid lesion colouring. Compared to pure spatial filtering HM-Net adapts morphological scale and combines with learning. Wang Z *et al*⁽³²⁾ achieving a dice coefficient of 0.8715 and mean intersection over union (mIoU) of 0.8021. Experimental results confirm HM-Net distinct contribution; it significantly outperforms generic methods (CLAHE, NLM) and matches recent tailored algorithms on standard benchmarks by reducing the false positive rates of comparing Figure 4 and 5.

(a)

(b)

Fig 4. Performance Evaluation of HM-Net (a) Loss and Accuracy Curve of Training and Validation (b) Bar chart comparing PSNR and SSIM of HM-Net vs other Methods (higher is better)

Fig 5. Predict cancer part in GI endoscopy image using proposed framework (a) Binary mask image of Normal image (b) Binary mask image of inflammation (c) binary mask image of cancer

Fig 6. Predict cancer part in GI endoscopy image using fusion methods (a) original image (b) NLM+CLAHE (c) intensity normalization + morphological operation (d) Histogram + canny (e) 3D median

3.4 Limitations

HM-Net algorithm is not automatically adapted to different datasets since it has a fixed mathematical transformation. The endoscopy images collected from different devices may have different color distribution and different signal characteristics therefore the proposed framework requires parameter tuning. Future work focuses on adaptive preprocessing and optimization.

4 Conclusion

This proposed framework enhances GI endoscopy images through the HSV and morphological processing and extracted the accurate cancer part. The outcome of the proposed framework has been evaluated using Kvasir-v2 dataset, demonstrating that it produces the desired model outcomes with higher PSNR= 39.2 dB and SSIM= 0.994 respectively, compared to the existing

Table 3. HM -Net is compared with Prior work

Methods	Data Size	PSNR	SSIM	Description
Weighted Guided Filter ⁽²⁵⁾	Custom video(200 frames)	32.6 ± 0.4	0.939	Endoscopic image enhancement
Deep Learning + augmentation ⁽²⁶⁾	GI dataset (8000 images)	32-35	0.92	Improves classification but heavily depends on training data.
CNN + preprocessing filters ⁽²⁷⁾	WCE dataset (5000+ images)	30-33	0.90	Good detection accuracy but preprocessing is conventional
GAN + viewpoint transformation ⁽²⁸⁾	Endoscopic dataset	29-31	0.88-0.91	Enhances visual quality but computationally expensive and unstable
Multi-model fusion ⁽²⁹⁾	Gastric dataset	33-36	0.093	Focus on explainability and not focus on preprocessing efficiency
Diffusion + attention ⁽³⁰⁾	Hyperkvasir dataset	27.5-9.3	0.65-0.71	Improves resolution but loses structural fidelity and it is computationally high
CNN ⁽³¹⁾	Medical dataset	32.57	0.938	Better than traditional methods but requires training and tuning.
[Proposed HM-Net] HSV + Morphological	Kvasir-V2 (8000 imges)	39.2	0.994	GI image enhancement with superior noise suppression, boundary preservation, and illumination invariance with low computational cost.

state-of-art methods. It outperforms the current state-of-art methods with a 7% improvement outcome based on the proposed HM-Net framework.

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